

A linearly implicit DG-ALE method for the evaporation of spherical fuel droplets

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Abstract

A novel method for the simulation of fuel droplets evaporating under spherical symmetry conditions is presented. The scheme considers a high-order discontinuous Galerkin method for the space discretization, which is combined with a moving mesh formulation so as to adequately track the droplet surface. A time-step adaptive, third-order, linearly implicit Runge–Kutta scheme is employed for the time discretization, so that it is only necessary to solve a linear system for each Runge–Kutta stage and large CFL numbers can be attained. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first paper on the application of high-order methods to the analysis of evaporating droplets. The method has been applied to the study of n-butanol, ethanol and n-heptane droplets, showing good agreement with the results reported by other authors.

Keywords: droplet evaporation, high-order methods, linearly implicit Runge–Kutta, arbitrary Lagrangian–Eulerian, discontinuous Galerkin, moving mesh

1. Introduction

The evaporation process of fuel droplets is a phenomenon with a significant effect on the combustion efficiency of liquid fuels, as well as on the production of pollutants such as unburned hydrocarbons, NO_x, CO, or particulate emissions. This is due to the fact that, to burn liquid fuels, these need first to be atomized, that is, separated into very small droplets forming a spray. The droplets are then injected into a combustion chamber filled by a hot gas, evaporate and mix with the gas before the combustion process takes place. Therefore, combustion performance becomes very sensitive to the space distribution of fuel vapors and temperatures resulting from the evaporation process [1, 2].

Under some simplifying assumptions, it is possible to obtain useful analytical or semi-analytical models addressing the evaporation of fuel droplets [2, 3]. However, for fully realistic models one must resort to numerical methods. For instance, Cho et al. [4], Cuoci et al. [5, 6], Borghesi and Mastorakos [7, 8] and Millán [9] have developed very detailed models using finite element, finite volume and finite difference schemes. In these works, the mesh is moved according to an arbitrary Lagrangian–Eulerian (ALE) formulation so as to track the interface between the droplet and the surrounding gas. The considered space discretizations are first or second-order accurate, and are combined with implicit time-marching backward differentiation formulas and related methods [10].

Fixed-mesh methods for droplet evaporation are due to Mitchell et al. [11], which transform the governing equations so that the computational domain stays fixed and apply a finite-difference scheme. This method is second-order accurate both in space and in time. Also, Schlottke and Weigand [12], Scapin et al. [13],

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Shang et al. [14] and Xu et al. [15] combine the finite difference or finite volume methods with the volume of fluid interface-capturing technique, and apply first-order or second-order time-marching formulas. Despite interface-capturing methods are more simple to implement and less expensive than moving mesh methods, they are less accurate concerning the interface location and the mass and energy conservation [16].

In the last years, the discontinuous Galerkin (DG) method [17–19] has received vast attention in the literature on Computational Fluid Dynamics. Indeed, in the presence of hyperbolic phenomena such as convection, it is easier to achieve numerical stability in comparison with the (continuous) finite element method. Also, it allows for high-order accurate schemes in a simpler and more rigorous way than in the case of the finite volume method. Finally, in contrast to the finite difference method, it is locally conservative. Since the motion of the interface between the droplet and the surrounding gas during the evaporation process is precisely a consequence of the conservation of mass and energy in the system, local conservation is therefore an essential property to adequately track and follow the former. There are some works on the DG method for multiphase flows including droplets [20–22]; however, these do not seem to consider the phase-change process.

Furthermore, the time-marching formulas considered by the methods above are either explicit, which results unstable in the presence of diffusion terms, or implicit, which requires the solution of a nonlinear system at each time step, becoming therefore computationally expensive. As a remedy, some authors propose to employ linearly implicit schemes [23–27]. These require only the solution of a few linear systems at each time step, hence reducing the computational time, and present good stability properties. In addition, the time step size can be adapted as in conventional explicit or implicit methods.

Motivated by the aforementioned facts, in this work a novel method for the simulation of evaporating droplets is presented. Its main features are:

- (i) The use of a DG-ALE formulation, which allows for high-order convergence rates with respect to mesh size (and hence for a reduction in the CPU time) and for an accurate tracking of the liquid–gas interface.
- (ii) The use of a third-order, adaptive, linearly implicit, time-stepping formula.

The method is formulated under the hypothesis of spherical symmetry, which is acceptable for small droplets and/or small relative velocity between the droplet and the gas, and of constant densities of the liquid and the gas.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the mathematical formulation of the problem, including all underlying assumptions and simplifications. Sections 3 and 4 describe the spatial and temporal discretization methods, respectively. Finally, Section 5 presents a set of numerical experiments used to validate the model, including comparisons with other models in the literature as well as tests of numerical convergence and computational efficiency.

2. Mathematical formulation

The following main hypothesis will be assumed:

- (i) the fuel droplet consists of a single compound,
- (ii) the droplet is isolated and vaporizes in an infinite, inert and stagnant atmosphere,
- (iii) the densities of the droplet and of the atmosphere are constant, as well as the mass and heat diffusion coefficients,
- (iv) effects due to forced convection and buoyancy can be neglected, endowing the problem with spherical symmetry.

Hence, for the numerical solution, a spherical domain of sufficiently large radius R^∞ is considered. The domain is divided in two regions: the liquid (l) phase occupies the sphere given by $0 \leq r < a(t)$, and the gas (g) phase occupies the region $a(t) < r < R^\infty$. Here, r denotes the distance to the origin, t the time, and $a(t)$ the radius of the droplet. The equations governing both phases, as well as the boundary and interface conditions [2, 3, 28], are reviewed next.

2.1. Gas phase

The gas phase is assumed to be a mixture of an environment gas (e) and fuel (f) vapor. Its behavior is governed by a system of conservation equations for the masses of these two components and for the energy, namely,

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_g}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 (v_g \mathbf{u}_g + \mathbf{f}_g^{\text{diff}}) \right) = \mathbf{0}, \quad \mathbf{u}_g := \begin{bmatrix} \varrho_{g,f} \\ \varrho_{g,e} \\ H_g \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{f}_g^{\text{diff}} \left(\mathbf{u}_g, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_g}{\partial r} \right) := \begin{bmatrix} J_{g,f} \\ J_{g,e} \\ q_g \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{u}_g = \mathbf{u}_g(r, t)$ is the vector of conservative variables, $\varrho_{g,f}$ and $\varrho_{g,e}$ denote respectively the masses of fuel and environmental gas per unit volume of the mixture, H_g is the total enthalpy per unit volume of the mixture (including latent heat of vaporization), $v_g(r, t)$ is the radial velocity, $J_{g,f}$ and $J_{g,e}$ are respectively the mass diffusion fluxes of fuel and environmental gas, and q_g is the heat flux.

The mass and heat fluxes are respectively given by Fick and Fourier laws, which can be written as (see also Appendix A)

$$J_{g,f} = -D_{M,g} \frac{\partial \varrho_{g,f}}{\partial r}, \quad J_{g,e} = -D_{M,g} \frac{\partial \varrho_{g,e}}{\partial r}, \quad q_g = -D_{T,g} \left(\frac{\partial H_g}{\partial r} - \frac{\partial \varrho_{g,f}}{\partial r} h_{g,f} - \frac{\partial \varrho_{g,e}}{\partial r} h_{g,e} \right), \quad (2)$$

where $D_{M,g}$ is the mass diffusion coefficient of the mixture, $D_{T,g}$ is the thermal diffusion coefficient, and $h_{g,f}$ and $h_{g,e}$ are respectively the enthalpies of the fuel and of the environmental gas per unit mass. The diffusion coefficients $D_{M,g}$ and $D_{T,g}$ are assumed constant; however, the mass enthalpies $h_{g,f}$ and $h_{g,e}$ depend on the vector of conservative variables \mathbf{u}_g , as it will be shown in Section 2.5. Note that radiative heating, Soret and Dufour effects are not considered.

It is a major assumption that the gas density $\rho_g = \varrho_{g,f} + \varrho_{g,e}$ is constant. In that case, it is well-known that mass conservation leads to a divergence-free velocity field, that is, $\partial(r^2 v_g)/\partial r = 0$. Integration of the latter yields a gas velocity field of the form

$$v_g(r, t) = v_g|_{r=a^+}(t) \frac{a^2(t)}{r^2}. \quad (3)$$

Here, $v_g|_{r=a^+}$ denotes the gas velocity at the droplet surface, which will be obtained from the interface conditions (Section 2.3).

Remark 1. *Since the gas density ρ_g is considered constant, in principle it would be possible to remove the equation for $\varrho_{g,e}$ from system (1), and deduce the value of the latter directly from $\varrho_{g,e} = \rho_g - \varrho_{g,f}$. However, here we prefer to keep all the equations in order to make the present formulation easier to extend to the case of temperature-dependent densities, as we plan to do in future works.*

2.2. Liquid phase

The liquid phase is assumed to be a mono-component fuel of constant density $\varrho_{l,f}$ ¹. Similarly to the gas phase, its behavior is described by the conservation system

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_l}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 (v_l \mathbf{u}_l + \mathbf{f}_l^{\text{diff}}) \right) = \mathbf{0}, \quad \mathbf{u}_l := \begin{bmatrix} \varrho_{l,f} \\ H_l \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{f}_l^{\text{diff}} \left(\mathbf{u}_l, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_l}{\partial r} \right) := \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ q_l \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where the notation is analogous to that of the gas phase. Since the liquid phase is mono-component, there is no mass diffusion and the heat flux reads simply

$$q_l = -D_{T,l} \frac{\partial H_l}{\partial r}. \quad (5)$$

¹The density of the liquid is denoted by $\varrho_{l,f}$, and not simply by ρ_l , in order to make the notation consistent with that of the gas phase.

114 Furthermore, for symmetry reasons, $v_l(0, t) = 0$ for all t . Therefore, in this case the constant density
115 restriction (or, equivalently, the divergence-free constraint $\partial(r^2 v_l)/\partial r = 0$) yields

$$v_l(r, t) = 0. \quad (6)$$

116 **Remark 2.** Since $v_l = 0$, the equation for $\varrho_{l,f}$ in system (4) reduces simply to $\partial \varrho_{l,f}/\partial t = 0$, as expected.
117 Despite this trivial equation could be removed from system (4), here we prefer to keep it due to the reason
118 discussed in Remark 1.

119 2.3. Boundary and interface conditions

120 In order to solve Eqs. (1) and (4) it is necessary to prescribe appropriate boundary conditions for both
121 the liquid and gas phases.

122 For the gas phase, since there are convection and diffusion effects (cf. Eq. (1)), it is necessary to prescribe,
123 for each conservative variable $\varrho_{g,f}$, $\varrho_{g,e}$ and H_g , one condition at the outermost boundary $r = R^\infty$ and one
124 condition at the outer side of the droplet surface, $r = a^+(t)$. Recall that it is also necessary to set the value
125 for the gas velocity at the droplet surface, $v_g|_{r=a^+}$ (cf. Eq. (3)). For the liquid phase, there is no convection
126 and no mass diffusion (cf. Eqs. (4) and (6)), so it is not possible to impose any boundary conditions for
127 the liquid density $\varrho_{l,f}$. (Indeed, the latter is constant in time and uniform in the space domain.) For the
128 enthalpy H_l , it is necessary to impose one condition at the innermost boundary $r = 0$ and one condition at
129 the inner side of the droplet surface $r = a^-(t)$, as there is heat diffusion. Also note that the velocity of the
130 droplet surface, $\dot{a}(t)$, is unknown. The number of conditions required by each variable is summarized in
131 Table 1.

Table 1: Number of conditions required by each variable at the different boundaries.

Variable	$r = 0,$	$r = a^-(t)$	$r = a^+(t)$	$r = R^\infty$
Fuel density	0	0	1	1
Environmental gas density	-	-	1	1
Enthalpy	1	1	1	1
Velocity	-	-	1	0

132 The boundary conditions at the inner and outermost boundaries are clear. At the innermost boundary
133 $r = 0$, radial symmetry is imposed, whereas at the outermost boundary $r = R^\infty$, a prescribed value \mathbf{u}_g^∞ that
134 represents the state of the gas far away from the droplet is imposed. Mathematically speaking,

$$\frac{\partial H_l}{\partial r}(0, t) = 0, \quad \mathbf{u}_g(R^\infty, t) = \mathbf{u}_g^\infty. \quad (7)$$

135 For brevity of notation, it is convenient to introduce the *matching operator*

$$\mathcal{M}_l : [\varrho_{l,f}, H_l]^T \mapsto [\varrho_{l,f}, 0, H_l]^T. \quad (8)$$

136 That is, $\mathcal{M}_l(\mathbf{u}_l)$ fills the vector \mathbf{u}_l with a zero that corresponds to the density $\varrho_{l,e}$ of environmental gas at
137 the liquid phase. In this way, the elements of $\mathcal{M}_l(\mathbf{u}_l)$ and \mathbf{u}_g correspond to the same physical variables,
138 and similarly happens if this operator is applied to the flux vector.

139 At the droplet surface, several interface conditions are imposed. First, since the droplet surface has no
140 mass nor energy, the mass and energy fluxes are constant across the former, that is,

$$\mathcal{M}_l \left(\left((v_l - \dot{a}) \mathbf{u}_l + \mathbf{f}_l^{\text{diff}} \left(\mathbf{u}_l, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_l}{\partial r} \right) \right)_{r=a^-} \right) = \left((v_g - \dot{a}) \mathbf{u}_g + \mathbf{f}_g^{\text{diff}} \left(\mathbf{u}_g, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_g}{\partial r} \right) \right)_{r=a^+}. \quad (9)$$

141 In addition, the temperature T_α , which is a known function of the densities and enthalpy (see Section 2.5),
142 is constant across the surface, i.e.,

$$T_l(\mathbf{u}_l|_{r=a^-}) = T_g(\mathbf{u}_g|_{r=a^+}). \quad (10)$$

143 For the evaporating fuel, assuming liquid-vapor thermodynamic equilibrium and Dalton's law for ideal gases,

$$p_{v,f}(\mathbf{u}_l|_{r=a^-}) \left(\frac{\varrho_{g,f}}{W_f} + \frac{\varrho_{g,e}}{W_e} \right) \Big|_{r=a^+} = p_T \frac{\varrho_{g,f}}{W_f} \Big|_{r=a^+} \quad (11)$$

144 holds, where p_T is the total pressure in the system, $p_{v,f}$ is the fuel vapor pressure, known as a function of
145 the liquid density and enthalpy (see Section 2.5), and W_f and W_e are respectively the molecular weights of
146 the fuel and of the environmental gas. Finally, the fixed value of the gas density is imposed via

$$\varrho_{g,f}|_{r=a^+} + \varrho_{g,e}|_{r=a^+} = \rho_g. \quad (12)$$

147 Relations (9)-(12) provide six scalar equations that allow to determine the required five boundary
148 equations at the droplet surface (cf. Table 1) plus the droplet surface velocity $\dot{a}(t)$.

149 In addition, it will be useful to compute the evaporated mass per unit time and surface through the
150 droplet surface,

$$\dot{m}'' := (v_l|_{r=a^-} - \dot{a})\varrho_{l,f} = (v_g|_{r=a^+} - \dot{a})\rho_g. \quad (13)$$

151 **Remark 3.** Since $v_l = 0$ (cf. Eq. (6)) and $\dot{m}'' > 0$ due to physical reasons, it is readily deduced from Eq.
152 (13) that $\dot{a} < 0$, that is, the droplet size decreases, as expected. From this equation and taking into account
153 that $\varrho_{l,f} > \rho_g$, it is also deduced that $v_g|_{r=a^+} = -\dot{a}(\varrho_{l,f}/\rho_g - 1) > 0$ and therefore $v_g(r, t) > 0$ (cf. Eq (3)).

154 2.4. Initial condition

155 An appropriate initial condition is also necessary to march in time Eqs. (1) and (4). Normally, this
156 is problem dependent. However, in this paper, the initial condition considered for all the numerical tests
157 is of the same form. The gas-phase is defined by the analytically integrated profiles of temperature and
158 composition available in [28]. For the liquid phase, the temperature is assumed to be uniform, except for
159 a boundary layer at the droplet surface which allows to satisfy the interface conditions. More details are
160 given in Appendix C.

161 2.5. Computation of thermodynamic properties

162 It is important to keep in mind that the DG method considers $\mathbf{u}_l = [\varrho_{l,f}, H_l]^T$ and $\mathbf{u}_g = [\varrho_{g,f}, \varrho_{g,e}, H_g]^T$
163 as discretization variables. Hence, in order to numerically solve the equations above, it is necessary to
164 provide numerical routines that evaluate the required nonconstant thermodynamic variables (namely, the
165 temperatures T_g and T_l , the mass enthalpies $h_{g,f}$ and $h_{g,e}$, and the fuel vapor pressure $p_{v,f}$) from the values
166 of \mathbf{u}_l and \mathbf{u}_g .

167 The mass enthalpies $h_{g,f} = h_{g,f}(T_g)$ and $h_{g,e} = h_{g,e}(T_g)$ are known functions of the temperature T_g of
168 the gas phase via the NASA polynomials [29]. At the same time, T_g is computed from $\mathbf{u}_g = [\varrho_{g,f}, \varrho_{g,e}, H_g]^T$
169 by solving the nonlinear system

$$H_g = \varrho_{g,f} h_{g,f}(T_g) + \varrho_{g,e} h_{g,e}(T_g)$$

170 with the Newton–Raphson method [30].

171 Similarly, the temperature T_l of the liquid is computed by solving

$$H_l = \varrho_{l,f} h_{l,f}(T_l),$$

172 where $h_{l,f}$ is the mass enthalpy of the fuel at the liquid phase, which is also computed from the temperature
173 T_l via [29]. Finally, the fuel vapor pressure $p_{v,f}$ is given by T_l via the database [31].

174 Recall that the rest of thermodynamic and transport properties (e.g., density or mass diffusion coefficient)
175 are treated as constants. Thus, these constant values are specifically calculated for each simulation by
176 evaluating properties at a given reference state. Namely, liquid properties are evaluated at the corresponding
177 wet bulb temperature [32], whereas gas-phase properties are obtained by applying the “1/3 rule”, recom-
178 mended in [33] for droplet evaporation studies. This rule requires temperature and composition both at the
179 droplet surface (assumed to be at wet bulb conditions) and at the bulk gas, far away from the droplet. Since
180 gas properties are calculated for a fuel-gas blend, mixture rules have to be applied. The database source for
181 each property and mixture rules used can be found in Appendix A4 of [34].

3. Space discretization

For brevity of notation, in what follows $\alpha = l, g$ will denote an arbitrary phase (i.e., liquid or gas), whereas $R_\alpha^i(t)$ and $R_\alpha^o(t)$ will denote respectively the inner and outer radius of the phase α . That is, $R_l^i(t) = 0$, $R_l^o(t) = R_g^i(t) = a(t)$ and $R_g^o(t) = R^\infty$. Also note that Eqs. (1) and (4) have a similar structure, namely,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{u}_\alpha(r, t) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \left(v_\alpha \mathbf{u}_\alpha + \mathbf{f}_\alpha^{\text{diff}} \left(\mathbf{u}_\alpha, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha}{\partial r} \right) \right) \right) = \mathbf{0}, \quad (14)$$

with $v_\alpha = v_\alpha(r, t)$ a given velocity field.

3.1. Computational mesh

For each phase α , the space domain $[R_\alpha^i, R_\alpha^o]$ is divided into a mesh of N_α^h elements defined by $N_\alpha^h + 1$ moving nodes $R_\alpha^i(t) = r_\alpha^1(t) < \dots < r_\alpha^{N_\alpha^h+1}(t) = R_\alpha^o(t)$. In order to track the droplet surface, the mesh nodes move with the velocities

$$\dot{r}_l^K(t) = \frac{r_l^K(t)}{a(t)} \dot{a}(t), \quad \dot{r}_g^K(t) = \frac{R^\infty - r_g^K(t)}{R^\infty - a(t)} \dot{a}(t), \quad K = 1, \dots, N_\alpha^h + 1. \quad (15)$$

That is, both for the liquid and the gas, the node placed at the droplet boundary $r = a(t)$ moves with the droplet velocity $\dot{a}(t)$, the node placed at the other boundary stays fixed, and the velocity of the rest of the nodes varies linearly with the radial coordinate r .

At the initial time $t^0 = 0$, the mesh is defined in such a way that the elements are smaller close to the droplet surface, where the gradients of the temperature and mass fractions are expected to be larger, to ensure the stability of the method. In particular, the initial coordinates of the liquid phase nodes are given by

$$r_l^K(t^0) = a^0 \left(1 - \frac{\exp\left(\eta_l \left(1 - \frac{K-1}{N_l^h}\right)\right) - 1}{\exp(\eta_l) - 1} \right), \quad K = 1, \dots, N_l^h,$$

whereas the initial coordinates of the gas phase nodes are

$$r_g^K(t^0) = a^0 + (R^\infty - a^0) \frac{\exp\left(\eta_g \frac{K-1}{N_g^h}\right) - 1}{\exp(\eta_g) - 1}, \quad K = 1, \dots, N_g^h,$$

where $a^0 = a(t^0)$. Here, $\eta_l > 0$ and $\eta_g > 0$ are user-defined parameters that regulate the degree of mesh refinement; if these values increase, so do the ratios between the largest and smallest elements sizes at each phase.

3.2. Basis functions

At each moving element $E_\alpha^K(t) := [r_\alpha^K(t), r_\alpha^{K+1}(t)]$, $K = 1, \dots, N_\alpha^h$, a set of polynomial basis functions $\{\phi_\alpha^{K,i}(r, t)\}_{i=0}^p$, with p the desired order for the space discretization, is defined. In particular, this is achieved by shifting the standard Legendre polynomials $\widehat{\phi}^0, \dots, \widehat{\phi}^p$ [35], defined in the interval $\widehat{E} = [-1, 1]$, to the moving element $E_\alpha^K(t)$ with an appropriate mapping F_α^K , that is,

$$\phi_\alpha^{K,i}(r, t)|_{r=F_\alpha^K(\xi, t)} := \widehat{\phi}^i(\xi), \quad F_\alpha^K(\xi, t) := \frac{r_\alpha^K(t) + r_\alpha^{K+1}(t)}{2} + \frac{r_\alpha^{K+1}(t) - r_\alpha^K(t)}{2} \xi, \quad \xi \in [-1, 1]. \quad (16)$$

Note that $F_\alpha^K(\xi, t)$ is linear with respect to ξ . Then, the exact solution \mathbf{u}_α to Eq. (14) is approximated at $E_\alpha^K(t)$ by a space semi-discrete solution \mathbf{u}_α^h of the form

$$\mathbf{u}_\alpha^h|_{E_\alpha^K}(r, t) = \sum_{j=0}^p \phi_\alpha^{K,j}(r, t) \mathbf{U}_\alpha^{K,j}(t), \quad (17)$$

with $\{\mathbf{U}_\alpha^{K,j}(t)\}_{j=0}^p$ the degrees of freedom at the moving element $E_\alpha^K(t)$. Note that continuity at the mesh nodes is not enforced.

By virtue of Eq. (16), the basis functions $\phi_\alpha^{K,i}(r,t)$ are constant along trajectories of the form $r = F_\alpha^K(\xi,t)$ whenever ξ is fixed [36, 37]. More precisely, taking the derivative with respect to time in Eq. (16) and applying the chain rule,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\phi_\alpha^{K,i}(r,t) \Big|_{r=F_\alpha^K(\xi,t)} \right) = \left(\frac{\partial \phi_\alpha^{K,i}(r,t)}{\partial r} \frac{\partial F_\alpha^K(\xi,t)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \phi_\alpha^{K,i}(r,t)}{\partial t} \right)_{r=F_\alpha^K(\xi,t)} = \frac{\partial \widehat{\phi}^i(\xi)}{\partial t} = 0$$

or, equivalently,

$$\frac{\partial \phi_\alpha^{K,i}(r,t)}{\partial t} + w_\alpha(r,t) \frac{\partial \phi_\alpha^{K,i}(r,t)}{\partial r} = 0, \quad (18)$$

where

$$w_\alpha(r,t) \Big|_{r=F_\alpha^K(\xi,t)} := \frac{\partial F_\alpha^K(\xi,t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\dot{r}_\alpha^K(t) + \dot{r}_\alpha^{K+1}(t)}{2} + \frac{\dot{r}_\alpha^{K+1}(t) - \dot{r}_\alpha^K(t)}{2} \xi, \quad \xi \in [-1, 1], \quad (19)$$

is the *mesh velocity*, that is, the velocity of the trajectories $r = F_\alpha^K(\xi,t)$, with constant ξ , forced by the motion of the mesh nodes.

Remark 4. Irrespective of the velocities \dot{r}_α^K of the mesh nodes, the mesh velocity w_α is element-wise linear, continuous along the phase α and satisfies $w_\alpha(r_\alpha^K(t), t) = \dot{r}_\alpha^K(t)$ for all $K = 1, \dots, N_\alpha^h + 1$. Furthermore, due to the particular choice (15) for the velocities of the mesh nodes, in this case $w_\alpha(r,t)$ is linear with r at the phase α .

See Fig. 1 for a scheme of the involved variables.

Figure 1: Variables associated with the moving mesh at two arbitrary time levels t^1 and t^2 . Given the trajectories of the mesh nodes (green), at each time t the transformation $r = F_K(\xi, t)$ maps from the reference element \widehat{E} (orange) to the moving element $E_\alpha^K(t)$ (blue). For a fixed ξ ($\xi = \pm 1/3$ in the figure), this transformation also defines trajectories of the form $r = F_K(\xi, t)$ (red), along which the basis functions $\phi_\alpha^{K,i}(r,t)$ are constant (cf. Eq. (18)). The mesh velocity w_α (cf. Eq. (19)) is the velocity of these trajectories.

3.3. DG-ALE formulation

Eq. (14) can be written as

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{u}_\alpha(r,t) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r^2 w_\alpha \mathbf{u}_\alpha) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \mathbf{f}_\alpha^{\text{ALE}} \left(\mathbf{u}_\alpha, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha}{\partial r} \right) \right) = \mathbf{0}, \quad (20)$$

with

$$\mathbf{f}_\alpha^{\text{ALE}} \left(\mathbf{u}_\alpha, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha}{\partial r} \right) := (v_\alpha - w_\alpha) \mathbf{u}_\alpha + \mathbf{f}_\alpha^{\text{diff}} \left(\mathbf{u}_\alpha, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha}{\partial r} \right), \quad (21)$$

the total flux relative to the mesh velocity w_α (cf. Eq. (19)). Following the arbitrary Lagrangian–Eulerian (ALE) formulation [36–40] and the incomplete interior penalty DG method [17, 41], Eq. (20) is now multiplied by $4\pi r^2 \phi_\alpha^{K,i}$ and integrated by parts on the moving element $E_\alpha^K(t) = [r_\alpha^K(t), r_\alpha^{K+1}(t)]$ taking into account Eq. (18). After some manipulation, it can be shown that the space semi-discretized solution \mathbf{u}_α^h satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \int_{E_\alpha^K} \phi_\alpha^{K,i} \mathbf{u}_\alpha^h 4\pi r^2 dr &= \int_{E_\alpha^K} \frac{\partial \phi_\alpha^{K,i}}{\partial r} \mathbf{f}_\alpha^{\text{ALE}} \left(\mathbf{u}_\alpha^h, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha^h}{\partial r} \right) 4\pi r^2 dr \\ &+ \phi_\alpha^{K,i} \Big|_{r=r_\alpha^K} \widehat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha^K \left(\mathbf{u}_\alpha^h, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha^h}{\partial r} \right) 4\pi (r_\alpha^K)^2 - \phi_\alpha^{K,i} \Big|_{r=r_\alpha^{K+1}} \widehat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha^{K+1} \left(\mathbf{u}_\alpha^h, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha^h}{\partial r} \right) 4\pi (r_\alpha^{K+1})^2, \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

for all the elements $K = 1, \dots, N_\alpha^h$ and all the basis functions degrees $i = 0, \dots, p$, with $\widehat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha^K$ a numerical flux approximating $\mathbf{f}_\alpha^{\text{ALE}}$ through the node $r_\alpha^K(t)$. Note that $\widehat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha^K$ leaves the element $E_\alpha^{K-1}(t)$ and enters the element $E_\alpha^K(t)$. For brevity of notation, only the dependence of the fluxes with \mathbf{u}_α^h and its space derivative are highlighted, although these depend also on other variables such as the droplet surface velocity (which appears in the formulation through the mesh velocity w_α).

Remark 5. According to Remark 3, $v_l = 0$, $v_g > 0$ and $\dot{a} < 0$. Therefore, all the mesh nodes move with negative radial velocity, i.e., $\dot{r}_\alpha^K < 0$ (cf. Eq. (15)), which implies that the mesh velocity $w_\alpha < 0$ (cf. Eq. (19)). As a consequence, the relative velocity between the fluid and the mesh satisfies $v_\alpha - w_\alpha > 0$ both for the liquid and gas phases.

The numerical flux $\widehat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha^K$ in Eq. (22) is chosen in such a way that guarantees numerical stability and is consistent with $\mathbf{f}_\alpha^{\text{ALE}}$. In particular, let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h,K-} &:= \mathbf{u}_\alpha^h \Big|_{E_\alpha^{K-1}}(r_\alpha^K, t), & \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h,K-}}{\partial r} &:= \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha^h \Big|_{E_\alpha^{K-1}}(r_\alpha^K, t)}{\partial r}, & K &= 2, \dots, N_\alpha^h + 1, \\ \mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h,K+} &:= \mathbf{u}_\alpha^h \Big|_{E_\alpha^K}(r_\alpha^K, t), & \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h,K+}}{\partial r} &:= \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha^h \Big|_{E_\alpha^K}(r_\alpha^K, t)}{\partial r}, & K &= 1, \dots, N_\alpha^h, \end{aligned}$$

denote the values of $\mathbf{u}_\alpha^h \Big|_{E_\alpha^{K-1}}$, $\mathbf{u}_\alpha^h \Big|_{E_\alpha^K}$ and their space derivatives at $r = r_\alpha^K(t)$; see also Fig. 2. Then, at the inner nodes (i.e., $K = 2, \dots, N_\alpha^h$),

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha^K \left(\mathbf{u}_\alpha^h, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha^h}{\partial r} \right) &:= (v_\alpha - w_\alpha)_{r=r_\alpha^K} \mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h,K-} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\mathbf{f}_\alpha^{\text{diff}} \left(\mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h,K-}, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h,K-}}{\partial r} \right) + \mathbf{f}_\alpha^{\text{diff}} \left(\mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h,K+}, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h,K+}}{\partial r} \right) \right) \\ &+ \sigma_\alpha^K (\mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h,K-} - \mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h,K+}). \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

That is, $\widehat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha^K$ comes from applying upwinding to the convective term of the flux $\mathbf{f}_\alpha^{\text{ALE}}$ (cf. Eq. (21) and Remark 5), taking the average of the diffusive term at $r = r_\alpha^K(t)$ and adding a penalty term to weakly enforce continuity. The penalty coefficient is defined from the mass and thermal diffusion coefficients $D_{M,\alpha}$ and $D_{T,\alpha}$ as

$$\sigma_\alpha^K := C_\sigma \frac{\max\{D_{M,\alpha}, D_{T,\alpha}\}}{h_\alpha^K/p}, \quad K = 1, \dots, N_\alpha^h + 1,$$

where $C_\sigma = 50$ is a penalty parameter and

$$h_\alpha^1 := r_\alpha^2 - r_\alpha^1, \quad h_\alpha^K := \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{r_\alpha^{K+1} - r_\alpha^K} + \frac{1}{r_\alpha^K - r_\alpha^{K-1}} \right) \right]^{-1}, \quad K = 2, \dots, N_\alpha^h, \quad h_\alpha^{N_\alpha^h+1} := r_\alpha^{N_\alpha^h+1} - r_\alpha^{N_\alpha^h},$$

is the average mesh size at the node r_α^K . Note that $\widehat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha^K(\mathbf{u}_\alpha^h, \partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha^h / \partial r) = \mathbf{f}_\alpha^{\text{ALE}}(\mathbf{u}_\alpha^h, \partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha^h / \partial r)$ if \mathbf{u}_α^h and its space derivative are continuous. The fluxes at the boundaries, $\widehat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha^1$ and $\widehat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha^{N_\alpha^h+1}$, are not given by (23), but by the prescribed boundary conditions, as it will be shown next.

Figure 2: Variables defined at the element faces.

As usual in the finite element methodology, the initial condition for the space-discretized equation (20), $\mathbf{u}_\alpha^h(r, 0)$, is given by the L^2 -projection of a given initial condition $\mathbf{u}_\alpha(r, 0)$, that is, by solving

$$\int_{E_\alpha^K} \phi_\alpha^{K,i} \mathbf{u}_\alpha^h(r, 0) = \int_{E_\alpha^K} \phi_\alpha^{K,i} \mathbf{u}_\alpha(r, 0), \quad K = 1, \dots, N_\alpha^h + 1, \quad i = 0, \dots, p, \quad (24)$$

with $\mathbf{u}_\alpha^h(r, 0)$ satisfying the ansatz (17).

3.4. Boundary conditions

Boundary conditions are weakly enforced at each phase via the numerical fluxes at the inner and outer boundaries, $\widehat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha^1$ and $\widehat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha^{N_\alpha^h+1}$ [17, 41].

The innermost boundary, which corresponds to the liquid phase, is placed at the origin, i.e., $r_l^1(t) = 0$. In that case, it is straightforward to see, via Eq. (22), that the value of $\widehat{\mathbf{f}}_l^1$ is irrelevant as it is cancelled by the factor $4\pi(r_l^1)^2 = 0$. In other words, the DG formulation naturally imposes radial symmetry conditions at $r = 0$, and there is no need to set any specific value for $\widehat{\mathbf{f}}_l^1$.

At the outermost boundary $r = R^\infty$, which corresponds to the $(N_g^h + 1)$ th node of the gas phase, the given Dirichlet conditions \mathbf{u}_g^∞ are applied (see Eq. (7)). This is achieved by imposing a numerical flux

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\mathbf{f}}_g^{N_g^h+1} \left(\mathbf{u}_g^h, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_g^h}{\partial r} \right) &:= (v_g - w_g)_{r=R^\infty} \mathbf{u}_g^{h,(N_g^h+1)-} + \mathbf{f}_g^{\text{diff}} \left(\mathbf{u}_g^{h,(N_g^h+1)-}, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_g^{h,(N_g^h+1)-}}{\partial r} \right) \\ &+ \sigma_\alpha^{N_g^h+1} \left(\mathbf{u}_g^{h,(N_g^h+1)-} - \mathbf{u}_g^\infty \right). \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

The thermodynamic states of the liquid and of the gas at the droplet surface, $\mathbf{u}_l|_{r=a^-}$ and $\mathbf{u}_g|_{r=a^+}$, which are still unknown, are weakly imposed as Dirichlet conditions via

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\mathbf{f}}_l^{N_l^h+1} \left(\mathbf{u}_l^h, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_l^h}{\partial r} \right) &:= (v_l - w_l)_{r=a^-} \mathbf{u}_l^{h,(N_l^h+1)-} + \mathbf{f}_l^{\text{diff}} \left(\mathbf{u}_l^{h,(N_l^h+1)-}, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_l^{h,(N_l^h+1)-}}{\partial r} \right) \\ &+ \sigma_\alpha^{N_l^h+1} \left(\mathbf{u}_l^{h,(N_l^h+1)-} - \mathbf{u}_l|_{r=a^-} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

$$\widehat{\mathbf{f}}_g^1 \left(\mathbf{u}_g^h, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_g^h}{\partial r} \right) := (v_g - w_g)_{r=a^+} \mathbf{u}_g|_{r=a^+} + \mathbf{f}_g^{\text{diff}} \left(\mathbf{u}_g^{h,1+}, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_g^{h,1+}}{\partial r} \right) + \sigma_\alpha^1 \left(\mathbf{u}_g|_{r=a^+} - \mathbf{u}_g^{h,1+} \right). \quad (27)$$

The states $\mathbf{u}_l|_{r=a^-}$ and $\mathbf{u}_g|_{r=a^+}$ are computed by solving the interface conditions, as shown next. Note that $w_l|_{r=a^-} = w_g|_{r=a^+} = \dot{a}$ in the equations above.

269 **Remark 6.** Recalling that $\mathbf{u}_l|_{r=a^-} = [\varrho_{l,f}, H_l|_{r=a^-}]^T$, the flux defined in (26) is weakly imposing, via the
 270 penalty term, a value $\varrho_{l,f}$ for the fuel density at the outer boundary of the liquid phase. However, according to
 271 Table 1, it is not necessary to impose this condition from a theoretical point of view. Therefore, in principle it
 272 is possible to replace the penalty term in (26) by $\mathcal{V}_l(\sigma_\alpha^{N_l^h+1}(\mathbf{u}_l^{h,(N_l^h+1)-} - \mathbf{u}_l|_{r=a^-}))$, with $\mathcal{V}_l : [\widehat{f}_\rho, \widehat{f}_H] \mapsto [0, \widehat{f}_H]$,
 273 so that no value is enforced for the density at the liquid outer boundary. Nevertheless, numerical experiments
 274 show that the results are satisfactory using the flux defined in (26).

275 3.5. Interface conditions

276 Up to this point, Eq. (22), together with Eq. (17) and the definitions of the fluxes (21)-(27), defines a
 277 set of ordinary differential equations for the degrees of freedom describing \mathbf{u}_l^h and \mathbf{u}_g^h . Likewise, the motion
 278 of the mesh nodes is given by the set of ordinary differential equations (15). However, the system is not
 279 closed, as there are some additional unknown variables related to the liquid–gas interface, namely:

- 280 (i) the vectors $\mathbf{u}_l|_{r=a^-} = [\varrho_{l,f}, H_l|_{r=a^-}]^T$, $\mathbf{u}_g|_{r=a^+} = [\varrho_{g,f}|_{r=a^+}, \varrho_{g,e}|_{r=a^+}, H_g|_{r=a^+}]^T$, which contain four
 281 unknown scalar variables, and which determine the boundary conditions at the interface (cf. (26)-
 282 (27)),
 - 283 (ii) the velocity of the gas at the droplet surface, $v_g|_{r=a^-}$, which determines the velocity field $v_g(r,t)$ via
 284 Eq. (3),
 - 285 (iii) the droplet surface velocity $\dot{a}(t)$, which determines the mesh velocity $w_\alpha(r,t)$ via Eqs. (15) and (19).
- 286 Recall that $\varrho_{l,f}$ is assumed constant and that $v_l(r,t) = 0$ (cf. Eq. (6)). Hence, Eqs. (15) and (22) are
 287 supplemented with six scalar equations; three of them stem from the continuity of the relative fluxes across
 288 the droplet surface (cf. Eq. (9)), which in terms of the matching operator \mathcal{M}_l (cf. Eq. (8)) and the DG
 289 discretization read in vector form as

$$\mathcal{M}_l(\widehat{\mathbf{f}}_l^{N_l^h+1}) = \widehat{\mathbf{f}}_g^1, \quad (28)$$

290 whereas the other three are the interface conditions (10)-(12).

291 Therefore, if the numerical solutions \mathbf{u}_l^h and \mathbf{u}_g^h are known, the interface variables above can be computed
 292 by solving (10)-(12) and (28), e.g., with the Newton–Raphson method [30]. In other words,

$$\mathbf{U}_a = \mathbf{U}_a(\mathbf{u}_l^h, \mathbf{u}_g^h) \quad (29)$$

293 where

$$\mathbf{U}_a := [H_l|_{r=a^-}, \varrho_{g,f}|_{r=a^+}, \varrho_{g,e}|_{r=a^+}, H_g|_{r=a^+}, v_g|_{r=a^+}, \dot{a}]^T \quad (30)$$

294 is the *interface variables vector*.

295 3.6. Matrix form of the equations

296 Following the DG methodology [17], Eq. (22) can be written in matrix form as

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\mathbb{M}_\alpha^h(\mathbf{R}_\alpha^h)\mathbf{U}_\alpha^h) = \mathbf{F}_\alpha^h(\mathbf{R}_\alpha^h, \mathbf{U}_\alpha^h, \mathbf{U}_a) \quad (31)$$

297 for each phase $\alpha = l, g$. Here, $\mathbb{M}_\alpha^h(\mathbf{R}_\alpha^h)$ is the mass matrix and $\mathbf{F}_\alpha^h(\mathbf{R}_\alpha^h, \mathbf{U}_\alpha^h, \mathbf{U}_a)$ is the generalized flux vector,
 298 which depend on a vector

$$\mathbf{R}_\alpha^h(t) := [r_\alpha^1(t), \dots, r_\alpha^{N_\alpha^h+1}(t)]^T \quad (32)$$

299 with the coordinates of the mesh nodes, on a vector \mathbf{U}_α^h collecting all the degrees of freedom of the DG
 300 discretization (see Eq. (B.5)), and on the interface variables vector \mathbf{U}_a (cf. Eq. (30)). See Appendix B for
 301 a more detailed description of \mathbb{M}_α^h and \mathbf{F}_α^h .

302 According to Eq. (15), the motion of the mesh nodes depends on \mathbf{R}_α^h and on the droplet surface velocity
 303 \dot{a} , that is, by a differential equation of the form

$$\frac{d\mathbf{R}_\alpha^h}{dt} = \dot{\mathbf{R}}_\alpha^h(\mathbf{R}_\alpha^h, \mathbf{U}_a), \quad (33)$$

304 where $\dot{\mathbf{R}}_\alpha^h := [\dot{r}_\alpha^1, \dots, \dot{r}_\alpha^{N_\alpha^h+1}]^T$ and \dot{r}_α^K is given by (15).

305 As explained in Section 3.5, the interface variables \mathbf{U}_a are obtained from the numerical solutions \mathbf{u}_l^h and
 306 \mathbf{u}_g^h by numerically solving the interface conditions (28), (10)-(12). In terms of the vector variables introduced
 307 above, this can be formally expressed as

$$\mathbf{U}_a = \mathbf{U}_a(\mathbf{R}_l^h, \mathbf{R}_g^h, \mathbf{U}_l^h, \mathbf{U}_g^h). \quad (34)$$

308 Replacing (34) in Eqs. (31) and (33) yields a system of ordinary differential equations for \mathbf{U}_l^h , \mathbf{U}_g^h , \mathbf{R}_l^h and
 309 \mathbf{R}_g^h , namely,

$$\frac{d}{dt} (\mathbb{M}_\alpha^h(\mathbf{R}_\alpha^h) \mathbf{U}_\alpha^h) = \mathbf{F}_\alpha^h(\mathbf{R}_\alpha^h, \mathbf{U}_\alpha^h, \mathbf{U}_a(\mathbf{R}_l^h, \mathbf{R}_g^h, \mathbf{U}_l^h, \mathbf{U}_g^h)), \quad (35)$$

$$\frac{d\mathbf{R}_\alpha^h}{dt} = \dot{\mathbf{R}}_\alpha^h(\mathbf{R}_\alpha^h, \mathbf{U}_a(\mathbf{R}_l^h, \mathbf{R}_g^h, \mathbf{U}_l^h, \mathbf{U}_g^h)), \quad (36)$$

310 with $\alpha = l, g$.

311 The initial condition $\mathbf{R}_\alpha^h(0)$ is readily given by the mesh coordinates at $t = 0$, whereas $\mathbf{U}_\alpha^h(0)$ is given by
 312 Eqs. (17) and (24).

313 4. Time discretization

314 4.1. Linearly implicit Runge–Kutta method

315 Diffusive terms and small mesh sizes cause Eq. (35) to be stiff. As a consequence, time-marching explicit
 316 methods would suffer from severe time step restrictions, whereas implicit methods would require to solve
 317 expensive nonlinear systems at each time step. To circumvent these drawbacks, a linearly implicit scheme
 318 [23–26] is used here.

319 Let $\mathbf{U}_\alpha^{h\tau}$ and $\mathbf{R}_\alpha^{h\tau}$ be the time-discretized solutions to (35)-(36) (that is, the time-discretized values of
 320 the DG discretization degrees of freedom and of the mesh nodes coordinates), and let ϕ^n denote an arbitrary
 321 variable ϕ evaluated at a given time instant t^n . Assuming the numerical solutions $\mathbf{R}_\alpha^{h\tau, n}$ and $\mathbf{U}_\alpha^{h\tau, n}$ at t^n
 322 are known, as well as the time step τ^n , to march to the next time level $t^{n+1} := t^n + \tau^n$, the stiff equation (35)
 323 is rewritten as

$$\frac{d}{dt} (\mathbb{M}_\alpha^h(\mathbf{R}_\alpha^h) \mathbf{U}_\alpha^h) = \mathbf{N}_\alpha^{h, n}(\mathbf{R}_l^h, \mathbf{R}_g^h, \mathbf{U}_l^h, \mathbf{U}_g^h) + \mathbb{J}_\alpha^{h, n} \mathbf{U}_\alpha^h, \quad (37)$$

$$\mathbf{N}_\alpha^{h, n}(\mathbf{R}_l^h, \mathbf{R}_g^h, \mathbf{U}_l^h, \mathbf{U}_g^h) := \mathbf{F}_\alpha^h(\mathbf{R}_\alpha^h, \mathbf{U}_\alpha^h, \mathbf{U}_a(\mathbf{R}_l^h, \mathbf{R}_g^h, \mathbf{U}_l^h, \mathbf{U}_g^h)) - \mathbb{J}_\alpha^{h, n} \mathbf{U}_\alpha^h, \quad (38)$$

324 where

$$\mathbb{J}_\alpha^{h, n} \approx \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_\alpha^h}{\partial \mathbf{U}_\alpha^h}(\mathbf{R}_\alpha^h, \mathbf{U}_\alpha^h, \mathbf{U}_a(\mathbf{R}_l^h, \mathbf{R}_g^h, \mathbf{U}_l^h, \mathbf{U}_g^h)) \quad (39)$$

325 is a (constant in (t^n, t^{n+1})) matrix that approximates the Jacobian of \mathbf{F}_α^h with respect to \mathbf{U}_α^h . This approx-
 326 imation is assumed sufficiently good so as to consider that the eigenvalues of

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{N}_\alpha^{h, n}}{\partial \mathbf{U}_\alpha^h}(\mathbf{R}_l^h, \mathbf{R}_g^h, \mathbf{U}_l^h, \mathbf{U}_g^h) = \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_\alpha^h}{\partial \mathbf{U}_\alpha^h}(\mathbf{R}_\alpha^h, \mathbf{U}_\alpha^h, \mathbf{U}_a(\mathbf{R}_l^h, \mathbf{R}_g^h, \mathbf{U}_l^h, \mathbf{U}_g^h)) - \mathbb{J}_\alpha^{h, n}$$

327 are small and therefore $\mathbf{N}_\alpha^{h, n}$ is nonstiff [25, 26]. In particular, to compute $\mathbb{J}_\alpha^{h, n}$, in this work the dependence
 328 of \mathbf{U}_a and of the thermodynamic properties on the numerical solution \mathbf{U}_α^h is ignored, and then $\partial \mathbf{F}_\alpha^h / \partial \mathbf{U}_\alpha^h$
 329 is evaluated at t^n [25–27, 42]. More details are given in Appendix B.

330 In that case, Eq. (37) can be marched in time with an implicit–explicit (IMEX) Runge–Kutta (RK)
 331 method, where the explicit part is used for the term $\mathbf{N}_\alpha^{h, n}$, which is nonlinear but nonstiff, whereas the
 332 implicit part is used for the term $\mathbb{J}_\alpha^{h, n} \mathbf{U}_\alpha^h$, which is stiff but linear. In this way, the scheme possesses strong
 333 stability features, involving only the solution of one linear system per stage.

354 which is solved via MATLAB's sparse LU factorization [46]. Note that (42) can be solved separately for
 355 each phase.

356 **Step 3: Solve for the interface variables.** Once $\mathbf{R}_\alpha^{h\tau,n,[i]}$ and $\mathbf{U}_\alpha^{h\tau,n,[i]}$ have been computed, it is
 357 possible to find the interface variables

$$\mathbf{U}_a^{n,[i]} := \mathbf{U}_a(\mathbf{R}_l^{h\tau,n,[i]}, \mathbf{R}_g^{h\tau,n,[i]}, \mathbf{U}_l^{h\tau,n,[i]}, \mathbf{U}_g^{h\tau,n,[i]})$$

358 by solving the interface conditions (cf. Section 3.5).

359 **Step 4: Compute generalized flux vector.** That is,

$$\mathbf{F}_\alpha^{h,n,[i]} := \mathbf{F}_\alpha^h(\mathbf{R}_\alpha^{h\tau,n,[i]}, \mathbf{U}_\alpha^{h\tau,n,[i]}, \mathbf{U}_a^{n,[i]}).$$

360 After all the stages have been solved, the solution at the next time level t^{n+1} is simply

$$\mathbf{R}_\alpha^{h\tau,n+1} = \mathbf{R}_\alpha^{h\tau,n,[s]}, \quad \mathbf{U}_\alpha^{h\tau,n+1} = \mathbf{U}_\alpha^{h\tau,n,[s]},$$

361 since the considered IMEX-RK scheme is globally stiffly accurate. Furthermore, to allow for time step
 362 adaptation, a lower-order accurate solution $\mathbf{U}_\alpha^{h\tilde{\tau},n+1}$ is computed with the embedded method, that is, by
 363 solving

$$\mathbb{M}_\alpha^{h,n,[s]} \mathbf{U}_\alpha^{h\tilde{\tau},n+1} = \mathbb{M}_\alpha^{h,n,[1]} \mathbf{U}_\alpha^{h\tau,n,[1]} + \tau^n \sum_{j=1}^s \tilde{b}_E^j \mathbf{F}_\alpha^{h,n,[j]} + \tau^n \sum_{j=1}^s (\tilde{b}_I^j - \tilde{b}_E^j) \mathbb{J}_\alpha^{h,n} \mathbf{U}_\alpha^{h\tau,n,[j]}.$$

364 Of course, the variables above $\mathbf{U}_\alpha^{h\tau,n+1}$ and $\mathbf{U}_\alpha^{h\tilde{\tau},n+1}$, together with $\mathbf{R}_\alpha^{h\tau,n+1}$, define respectively the
 365 (element-wise continuous) solutions $\mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h\tau,n+1}$ and $\mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h\tilde{\tau},n+1}$ via (17).

366 4.2. Adaptive time-stepping

367 To reduce the number of solved time intervals while keeping accuracy, the time step size is adapted
 368 following the standard procedure in Runge–Kutta methods [43], see also [25]. First, the error due to
 369 the integration in the time interval (t^n, t^{n+1}) (starting from an initial condition $\mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h\tau,n}$) is estimated by
 370 comparing the high and low-order solutions, $\mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h\tau,n+1}$ and $\mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h\tilde{\tau},n+1}$. In particular [25], it is estimated by
 371 $\mathcal{E}_T^n := \max\{\mathcal{E}_{T,l}^n, \mathcal{E}_{T,g}^n\}$, where

$$\mathcal{E}_{T,l}^n := \sqrt{\frac{1}{2|\Omega_l^{n+1}|} \int_{\Omega_l^{n+1}} \left[\left(\frac{\varrho_{l,f}^{h\tau,n+1} - \varrho_{l,f}^{h\tilde{\tau},n+1}}{\text{NF}_{\varrho_{l,f}}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{H_l^{h\tau,n+1} - H_l^{h\tilde{\tau},n+1}}{\text{NF}_{H_l}} \right)^2 \right] d\Omega}, \quad (43)$$

$$\mathcal{E}_{T,g}^n := \sqrt{\frac{1}{3|\Omega_g^{n+1}|} \int_{\Omega_g^{n+1}} \left[\left(\frac{\varrho_{g,f}^{h\tau,n+1} - \varrho_{g,f}^{h\tilde{\tau},n+1}}{\text{NF}_{\varrho_{g,f}}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\varrho_{g,e}^{h\tau,n+1} - \varrho_{g,e}^{h\tilde{\tau},n+1}}{\text{NF}_{\varrho_{g,e}}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{H_g^{h\tau,n+1} - H_g^{h\tilde{\tau},n+1}}{\text{NF}_{H_g}} \right)^2 \right] d\Omega}. \quad (44)$$

372 Here, NF_ϕ denotes an user-defined *normalization factor* that weights the contribution of an arbitrary variable
 373 ϕ to the total error. In principle, NF_ϕ should be a ‘‘characteristic value’’ of ϕ ; for instance, $\text{NF}_\phi = \sup|\phi(\cdot, 0)|$
 374 as is the case of this work. Furthermore, Ω_l^{n+1} and Ω_g^{n+1} denote respectively the sphere and the spherical
 375 shell occupied by liquid and gas phases at t^{n+1} .

376 If the error estimator \mathcal{E}_T^n is larger than a maximum, user-defined, value Tol_T , then the solution at t^{n+1}
 377 is discarded, the time step is modified as

$$\tau^n \leftarrow \tau^n \max \left\{ 0.2, \left(\frac{0.8\text{Tol}_T}{\mathcal{E}_T^n} \right)^{1/q} \right\},$$

378 and the solution at the new time level $t^{n+1} = t^n + \tau^n$ is computed again. Recall that q is the order of accuracy
 379 of the IMEX-RK method. Otherwise, the solution at t^{n+1} is accepted and a new time step

$$\tau^{n+1} = \tau^n \min \left\{ \left(\frac{0.8\text{Tol}_T}{\mathcal{E}_T^n} \right)^{1/q}, 2 \right\}$$

380 is set.

5. Numerical experiments

Next, the performance of the method is assessed through a series of numerical experiments, using to that end three compounds (n-butanol, ethanol and n-heptane) vaporizing under different conditions. The initial conditions for all these experiments are based on the analytical solution for the gas phase under the quasi-steady assumption [28]. This provides the required initial profiles of temperature and composition for the gas. As for the liquid, the initial temperature profile is assumed to follow an exponential shape such that most of the droplet remains at a uniform temperature T_0 , while the temperature rises sharply near the surface to satisfy coupling conditions. More details on initial conditions can be found in Appendix Appendix C.

Concerning the space-time discretization, unless otherwise specified, the outermost radius for the numerical experiments presented in this section is $R^\infty = 3000 a_0$, the number of elements in liquid and gas are $N_l^h = 40$ and $N_g^h = 160$, $p = 5$, the initial time step is $\tau_0 = 10^{-7}$ s, $\eta_g = 8.3$ and $\eta_l = 4.0$ are used to determine the initial coordinates of the mesh nodes, and $\text{Tol}_T = 10^{-4}$. Every numerical experiment has been carried out using an AMD EPYC 7662 2GHz machine with 16GB of RAM.

For each of the numerical experiments carried out in this section, the maximum CFL number is analyzed. The latter is defined as

$$\text{CFL}^{\max} := \max_{\alpha \in \{l, g\}} \max_{0 \leq n < N^t} \max_{K=1, \dots, N_\alpha^h} \max \left\{ \frac{\|v_\alpha^n - w_\alpha^n\|_{L^\infty(E_\alpha^K)} \tau^n}{h^K/p}, \frac{\max\{D_{T,\alpha}, D_{M,\alpha}\} \tau^n}{(h^K/p)^2}, \left\| \frac{\partial w_\alpha^n}{\partial r} \right\|_{L^\infty(E_\alpha^K)} \tau^n \right\}, \quad (45)$$

Note that a term related to the mesh distortion [37, 47] has been included. The condition $\text{CFL}^{\max} > 1$ is required for this method to be considered efficient; otherwise, it has no advantage over standard explicit methods.

5.1. N-butanol evaporation

This first test considers a n-butanol droplet, which initially has a diameter $d_0 = 500 \mu\text{m}$ and a temperature $T_0 = 300 \text{ K}$, evaporating in quiescent N_2 at $T^\infty = 1400 \text{ K}$. The values for the thermophysical and transport properties used in this simulation (as calculated by the criteria and databases described in Section 2.5) are provided in Appendix D.

Firstly, for a monocomponent droplet vaporizing under constant temperature conditions, it is expected that the droplet diameter squared decreases linearly with time, thus complying with the well-known d^2 law [28]. Fig. 3a clearly displays this behavior, with a practically constant evaporation rate, $K = -d(d^2)/dt$ once the initial heat-up transient of the droplet is completed. The results obtained with the current evaporation model are compared in this figure with those from the model presented in [48], also operating under the constant-property assumption. A remarkable agreement can be observed, with both models showing practically coincident droplet evaporation curves. A similar level of agreement can be inferred from Fig. 3b, which shows the temporal evolution of the evaporation mass flow rate. As for the CFL condition, the simulation performed for this numerical experiment obtained a $\text{CFL}^{\max} = 150$, which shows the improvement achieved by using the linearly implicit RK method over a standard explicit method.

Figure 3: Temporal evolution of relevant variables for a drop of n-butane vaporizing in quiescent N_2 at $T^\infty=1400$ K.

415 Since both models share exactly the same properties, the small differences between both in Fig. 3 can be
 416 ascribed to the different treatment of the gas-phase. Whereas the current model considers the gas phase to be
 417 transient (see time-derivative term in Eq. 1), the model in [48] assumes it to be quasi-steady. Reference [49]
 418 evaluates the importance of this term, concluding that the quasi-steady assumption slows down evaporation
 419 during the early stages of the droplet lifetime, accelerating it in the final phase. These observations are fully
 420 consistent with the minor differences between models shown in Fig. 3b.

421 More detailed insight into the physical process can be obtained from the temporal evolution of the droplet
 422 temperature in Fig. 4a. As expected, the droplet surface temperature, T_s , increases rapidly during the
 423 initial stage of its lifetime, until reaching a quasi-steady state condition in which all the heat flux entering
 424 the droplet is employed exclusively to vaporize the fuel, and therefore there is no further temperature
 425 increase. Fig. 4b displays the radial profiles of temperature inside the droplet at different instants: $t =$
 426 0.01, 0.05, 0.10, 0.20, 0.40 and 0.75 s. Starting from a practically flat profile at $t = 0$ (see Appendix C),
 427 the heat transferred to the droplet causes an abrupt increase in temperature close to the droplet surface.
 428 Non-negligible temperature gradients exist inside the droplet during the initial heat-up transient (i.e., before
 429 $t = 0.4$ s in Fig. 4b), pointing to the importance of considering finite liquid conductivity, even for low boiling
 430 point fuels such as n-butanol.

Figure 4: Temporal evolution of T_s (left) and radial profiles of temperature inside the droplet at different time instants (right).

431 5.2. Ethanol evaporation

432 The second experiment will address the evaporation of a $500 \mu\text{m}$ droplet of ethanol in quiescent N_2 ,
 433 replicating the cases presented in [50] for atmospheric pressure and different gas temperatures. The property
 434 values for each case are provided in Appendix D.

435 Due to space constraints, a detailed comparison is only presented for the high-temperature case, where
 436 $T^\infty = 1000\text{K}$ (arguably, the most relevant condition for real applications such as spray combustion). Despite
 437 the differences that could be *a priori* expected between models that rely on different property databases,
 438 as well as on different hypotheses and assumptions (e.g., [50] considers time-dependent properties), the
 439 agreement between both models in Fig. 5 can be considered as notable, both in terms of trends and
 440 numerical values. To quantify the differences, three metrics are used to characterize the droplet behavior:
 441 quasi-steady evaporation rate (K_{ss}), quasi-steady temperature at the surface ($T_{s,ss}$) and t_{10} (time required
 442 to reduce $(d/d_0)^2$ to 0.1). The values for these metrics, as calculated by both models, can be found in Table
 443 2 for all the cases explored in [50]. As it can be assessed, the differences between models are minor, with
 444 deviations always below 3.5% for any metric at any test condition.

445 Finally, it is worth noting that the CFL^{max} values achieved for the four simulations performed in this
 446 section are 1500, 460, 260 and 180 (for $T_\infty=400, 600, 800$ and 1000 K, respectively). Again, their high values
 447 confirm the strong stability of the numerical method.

Figure 5: Temporal evolution of relevant variables for a drop of ethanol vaporizing in quiescent N_2 at $T^\infty = 1000 K$.

Table 2: Comparison between models in terms of the three proposed metrics. The relative differences (in %) are shown in parentheses after the value of the metric obtained with the current model.

Model by [50]				Present model		
T_∞ [K]	K_{ss} [mm^2/s]	$T_{s,ss}$ [K]	t_{10} [s/mm^2]	K_{ss} [mm^2/s]	$T_{s,ss}$ [K]	t_{10} [s/mm^2]
400	0.0254	302.15	35.933	0.0257 (1.2%)	302.17 (0.0%)	35.119 (-2.3%)
600	0.0771	316.17	12.057	0.0794 (3.0%)	318.11 (0.6%)	11.647 (-3.4%)
800	0.1327	323.44	7.031	0.1355 (2.1%)	325.02 (0.5%)	6.854 (-2.5%)
1000	0.1947	328.33	4.793	0.1916 (-1.6%)	328.98 (0.2%)	4.842 (1.0%)

448 5.3. N-heptane evaporation

449 This third experiment will address the evaporation of a $500 \mu m$ droplet of n-heptane in quiescent air,
 450 replicating the cases presented in [51] for 600, 800 and 1000 K. Analogously to previous experiments, the
 451 thermophysical properties for each case have been calculated by following the criteria described in Section
 452 2.5, being numerical values listed in Appendix D.

453 As in the previous section, the comparison between the models' results is presented in terms of relevant
 454 variables, i.e., the quasi-steady evaporation rate (K_{ss}) and the quasi-steady temperature at the surface
 455 ($T_{s,ss}$). Table 3 displays the values obtained with both models for the three explored conditions. Once
 456 again, an excellent agreement is observed, further validating the present model.

457 On a final note, the CFL^{\max} values for the three simulations presented here are found to be 1970, 1280
 458 and 980 (for $T^\infty=600, 800$ and 1000 K, respectively).

Table 3: Comparison between models in terms of the proposed metrics. The relative differences (in %) are shown in parentheses after the value of the metric obtained with the current model.

Model by [51]			Present model	
T^∞ [K]	K_{ss} [mm^2/s]	$T_{s,ss}$ [K]	K_{ss} [mm^2/s]	$T_{s,ss}$ [K]
600	0.171	335	0.168 (-1.7%)	335 (-0.0%)
800	0.257	342	0.255 (-0.8%)	341 (-0.3%)
1000	0.332	346	0.328 (-1.2%)	344 (-0.6%)

5.4. Numerical convergence

For the droplet evaporation problem considered in this work, analytical solutions that can be used as reference are still not known. Hence, Richardson's extrapolation [9] is employed in order to check the convergence rates of the method with respect to the space and time discretizations. In particular, if ϕ^{ex} is the exact value of an arbitrary variable ϕ , and $\phi^{h\tau}$ is the space-time discretized solution, one should expect that [17, 25, 43]

$$\phi^{h\tau} = \phi^{\text{ex}} + \mathcal{O}(h^{p+1}) + \mathcal{O}(\tau^q),$$

where $h := R^\infty / (N_l^h + N_g^h)$ is the average mesh size and $\tau := \text{mean}(\tau^0, \tau^1, \dots)$ is the average time step size.

To analyze the convergence rate with respect to the mesh size h , a very small time tolerance Tol_T is considered, so that the error due to the time discretization is negligible. Then, it is assumed that $\phi^{h\tau} = \tilde{\phi} + \tilde{\phi}Ch^{\text{EOC}}$, where $\tilde{\phi}$ is a (EOC + 1)th order approximation to the exact solution ϕ^{ex} , C is a constant, and EOC denotes the *experimental order of convergence*. Note that $Ch^{\text{EOC}} =: e_S^{h\tau}$ is an estimation of the relative space discretization error. Given three numerical solutions, $\phi^{h\tau}$, $\phi^{h/2,\tau}$ and $\phi^{h/4,\tau}$, corresponding to three different mesh sizes h , $h/2$ and $h/4$, it is straightforward to show that

$$\text{EOC} = \log_2 \left(\frac{\phi^{h\tau} - \phi^{h/2,\tau}}{\phi^{h/2,\tau} - \phi^{h/4,\tau}} \right), \quad \tilde{\phi} = \frac{\phi^{h\tau} - 2^{\text{EOC}} \phi^{h/2,\tau}}{1 - 2^{\text{EOC}}}, \quad e_S^{h\tau} = \frac{\phi^{h\tau} - \tilde{\phi}}{\tilde{\phi}}. \quad (46)$$

In particular, the evaporation of a n-butanol droplet (cf. Section 5.1) is studied again, this time for a fixed final time $t_f = 0.05\text{s}$, setting $\text{Tol}_T = 10^{-7}$ and elements of degree $p = 3$, and choosing as reference variable ϕ the droplet surface temperature T_s at t_f . The results are presented in Table 4. As it can be seen, $\text{EOC} = 4.2957$, which is close to the expected value $p + 1$ [17]. Also note that the errors are very small; this is possible due to the use of high-order elements.

Table 4: Error estimation and order of accuracy of the space discretization with $p = 3$.

$N_l^h + N_g^h$	h [mm]	$T_s^{h\tau}$ [K]	\tilde{T}_s [K]	$e_S^{h\tau}$	EOC	CFL^{\max}	CPU time [s]
50	15.00	358.18761	358.10620	2.27E-04	4.30	3.0E-02	3.23E+05
100	7.50	358.11036	.	1.16E-05	.	5.0E-02	5.89E+05
200	3.75	358.10643	.	5.89E-07	.	1.1E-01	1.21E+06

The convergence rate with respect to the time discretization is studied in a similar fashion. First, a very fine mesh is considered, so that the space error is negligible. Then, a relation of the form $\phi^{h\tau} := \tilde{\phi} + \tilde{\phi}e_T^{h\tau}$, $e_T^{h\tau} = C\tau^{\text{EOC}}$ is assumed, where the coefficients $\tilde{\phi}$ and EOC and the time error estimation $e_T^{h\tau}$ are computed as

$$\text{EOC} = \log_2 \left(\frac{\phi^{h\tau} - \phi^{h,\tau/2}}{\phi^{h,\tau/2} - \phi^{h,\tau/4}} \right), \quad \tilde{\phi} = \frac{\phi^{h\tau} - 2^{\text{EOC}} \phi^{h,\tau/2}}{1 - 2^{\text{EOC}}}, \quad e_S^{h\tau} = \frac{\phi^{h\tau} - \tilde{\phi}}{\tilde{\phi}}.$$

from the numerical results $\phi^{h\tau}$, $\phi^{h,\tau/2}$ and $\phi^{h,\tau/4}$ that correspond to three different time step sizes τ , $\tau/2$ and $\tau/4$. Namely, new simulations of the n-butanol droplet are performed, setting $t_f = 0.7\text{s}$, $N_l^h + N_g^h = 200$ elements of degree $p = 3$, and $\tau = 10^{-5}\text{s}$. Time step adaptation is disabled in order to make the analysis easier. The results obtained are shown in Table 5, where it can be observed that $\text{EOC} = 2.94 \approx 3$, the expected value for the time discretization employed [45].

Table 5: Error estimation and order of accuracy of the time discretization.

τ	$T_s^{h\tau}$ [K]	\tilde{T}_s [K]	$e_S^{h\tau}$	EOC	CFL^{\max}	CPU time [s]
1.0E-05	364.460629	364.469695	2.37E-05	2.94	4.1E+03	1.47E+04
5.0E-06	364.468512	.	2.09E-06	.	2.2E+03	1.57E+04
2.5E-06	364.469541	.	7.36E-07	.	1.2E+03	2.97E+04

486 In addition, Tables 4 and 5 show the values of CFL^{\max} . For dominant space errors (Table 4), $\text{CFL}^{\max} < 1$.
 487 This is due to the very small time tolerance set in order to make the time discretization errors negligible,
 488 which leads to extremely small time steps. In contrast, for dominant time errors (Table 5), CFL^{\max} is large,
 489 confirming the strong stability of the model. The size of the time step also affects the time required to
 490 perform a simulation, which can be seen in the differences between the CPU time values in Tables 4 and 5.

491 5.5. Computational efficiency

492 Next the computational efficiency of the method is discussed. More specifically, the lifetime of a n-
 493 butanol droplet (cf. Section 5.1) has been computed for different values of the number of degrees of freedom
 494 (NDOF) and of the space discretization order p . The time tolerance is set to setting $\text{Tol}_T = 10^{-7}$ in order
 495 to analyze the effect of the space discretization. Then, the total CPU time, as well as the total times spent
 496 calculating the term \mathbf{F}_α^h in (31), the Jacobian matrix associated with this term (Eq. (39)), the factorization
 497 of the linear system matrix in (42), and the solution of linear system (42) have been measured.

498 Results are presented in Table 6. It can be seen the tasks that require the most time are the computation
 499 of the flux vector and of the Jacobian, as well as the factorization of the latter, whereas the solution of the
 500 linear systems is not very expensive. This is to be expected since only one linear system has to be solver per
 501 Runge–Kutta stage, and furthermore this operation is fast once the system matrix has been factorized. Also,
 502 for the same NDOF and higher p , the Jacobian matrix is less sparse and the computational cost increases,
 503 as can be checked in the table.

Table 6: Average computation times (in seconds) per time step for each simulation.

p	NDOF	Total	Flux vector comp.	Jacobian comp.	Matrix fact.	Linear solv.
1	100	6.09E-02	5.77E-03	5.00E-03	1.28E-03	5.88E-05
1	200	8.46E-02	3.14E-03	6.53E-03	3.25E-03	1.12E-04
1	400	1.43E-01	4.76E-03	1.12E-02	8.78E-03	2.72E-04
3	100	1.62E-01	6.13E-03	2.78E-02	4.89E-03	1.91E-04
3	200	1.90E-01	1.24E-02	3.43E-02	7.26E-03	2.78E-04
3	400	2.46E-01	9.43E-03	4.41E-02	1.62E-02	5.48E-04
3	800	3.56E-01	1.17E-02	5.75E-02	3.26E-02	1.08E-03
5	150	2.52E-01	9.30E-03	6.21E-02	9.06E-03	3.43E-04
5	300	3.17E-01	9.66E-02	6.17E-02	6.89E-03	2.45E-04
5	600	4.14E-01	2.39E-02	1.04E-01	3.13E-02	1.06E-03

504 The space discretization errors $e_S^{h\tau}$ associated with the cases considered in Table 6 have also been com-
 505 puted using Eq. (46), considering again as reference variable ϕ the droplet surface temperature T_s at the
 506 final time. Fig. 6 illustrates the relation between the error and the total CPU time required. It can be seen
 507 that, if high accuracy is not required, the most efficient option is to use $p = 1$. However, if smaller errors
 508 are required, the computational cost of using $p = 1$ becomes excessively high. In that case, setting $p = 3$ for
 509 intermediate accuracy and $p = 5$ for high accuracy results much more efficient.

Figure 6: Space discretization error $e_S^{h\tau}$ versus total CPU time (s) required to solve the n-butanol droplet evaporation problem.

6. Conclusions

In this work, a novel method for the solution of spherical evaporating droplets is presented. One of its main features is the use of a high-order DG method for the space discretization. As shown in the numerical experiments section, this allows for an increased efficiency if small errors are required, and therefore may pose a significant advantage over previous low-order methods employed for this problem [4–9]. In addition, the method considers a linearly implicit Runge–Kutta time-marching scheme [23–26], which allows for large CFL numbers and requires only the solution of a linear system of equations per Runge–Kutta stage.

The method has been validated against various cases concerning n-butanol, ethanol and n-heptane droplet vaporization, applying different test conditions. The results show good agreement with respect to other numerical models in the literature, both for the steady state and for the transient period, as well as the expected convergence rates with respect to the mesh size and the time step. The current method also displays clear advantages when compared to available analytical descriptions, which typically rely on stronger assumptions (e.g., quasi-steady gas phase or infinite thermal conductivity in the liquid).

There is ongoing work to address some limitations of the model, namely that the density and other thermophysical properties are considered constant, and that the fuel droplets are composed of only one species. Also, it would be of interest to implement mesh adaptation techniques [25, 52] in order to further increase the computational efficiency. Future developments will also focus on incorporating gas-phase chemical reactions into the model. In this context, the present formulation provides a robust and flexible numerical framework upon which these extensions can be systematically developed.

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Appendix A. On the mass and heat fluxes

Normally, Fick and Fourier laws are written as [28]

$$J_{g,f} = -\rho_g D_{M,g} \frac{\partial Y_{g,f}}{\partial r}, \quad J_{g,e} = -\rho_g D_{M,g} \frac{\partial Y_{g,e}}{\partial r}, \quad q_g = -\kappa_g \frac{\partial T_g}{\partial r},$$

536 with $\rho_g = \varrho_{g,f} + \varrho_{g,e}$ the gas mixture density, $Y_{g,f}$ the mass fraction of fuel, $Y_{g,e}$ the mass fraction of
 537 environmental gas, κ_g the thermal conductivity and T_g the temperature.

538 However, with a view to its numerical implementation, it is convenient to write these expressions in terms
 539 of gradients of the conservative variables $\varrho_{g,f}$, $\varrho_{g,e}$ and H_g . Since ρ_g is assumed constant, $\varrho_{g,f} = Y_{g,f}\rho_g$ and
 540 $\varrho_{g,e} = Y_{g,e}\rho_g$, it is clear that $J_{g,f}$ and $J_{g,e}$ can be written as in Eq. (2). For the heat flux, the thermodynamic
 541 relation

$$dH_g = d(\varrho_{g,f}h_{g,f} + \varrho_{g,e}h_{g,e}) = d\varrho_{g,f}h_{g,f} + d\varrho_{g,e}h_{g,e} + \varrho_{g,f}c_{p,g,f}dT_g + \varrho_{g,e}c_{p,g,e}dT_g,$$

542 with $c_{p,g,f}$ and $c_{p,g,e}$ the specific heat at constant pressure of the fuel and of the environmental gas, is
 543 employed. Noting that the specific heat of the mixture $c_{p,g}$ is defined so that $\rho_g c_{p,g} := \varrho_{g,f}c_{p,g,f} + \varrho_{g,e}c_{p,g,e}$,
 544 and that $D_{T,g} := \kappa_g/(\rho_g c_{p,g})$, the latter equation yields

$$dT_g = \frac{1}{\rho_g c_{p,g}} (dH_g - d\varrho_{g,f}h_{g,f} - d\varrho_{g,e}h_{g,e}),$$

545 and therefore Eq. (2).

546 Appendix B. Matrices of the DG discretization

547 As usual in the DG methodology, for the numerical implementation, the equations are rewritten in terms
 548 of the coordinate $\xi \in \widehat{E} = [-1, 1]$ by applying the change of variables $r = F_\alpha^K(\xi, t)$ (cf. Eq. (16)). In that
 549 case, the shape functions $\phi_\alpha^{K,i}(r, t)$ read simply as the Legendre polynomials $\widehat{\phi}^i(\xi)$, whereas the solution and
 550 its space derivative are written as

$$\mathbf{u}_\alpha(r, t)|_{r=F_\alpha^K(\xi, t)} = \sum_{j=0}^p \widehat{\phi}^j(\xi) \mathbf{U}_\alpha^{K,j}(t), \quad \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha(r, t)}{\partial r} \right|_{r=F_\alpha^K(\xi, t)} = \frac{1}{J_\alpha^K(t)} \sum_{j=0}^p \frac{\partial \widehat{\phi}^j(\xi)}{\partial \xi} \mathbf{U}_\alpha^{K,j}(t), \quad (\text{B.1})$$

551 with

$$J_\alpha^K(t) := \frac{\partial F_\alpha^K(\xi, t)}{\partial \xi} = \frac{r_\alpha^{K+1}(t) - r_\alpha^K(t)}{2}$$

552 the Jacobian of the transformation F_α^K . Furthermore, using (B.1), Eq. (22) reads

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\sum_{j=0}^p M_\alpha^{K,i,j} \mathbf{U}_\alpha^{K,j} \right) = \mathbf{F}_\alpha^{K,i}, \quad (\text{B.2})$$

553 for $K = 1, \dots, N_\alpha^h$, $i = 0, \dots, p$, where

$$\begin{aligned} M_\alpha^{K,i,j} &:= 4\pi J_\alpha^K \int_{\widehat{E}} \widehat{\phi}^i \widehat{\phi}^j (F_\alpha^K)^2 d\xi, \\ \mathbf{F}_\alpha^{K,i} &:= 4\pi \int_{\widehat{E}} \frac{d\widehat{\phi}^i}{d\xi} \mathbf{f}_\alpha^{\text{ALE}} \left(\mathbf{u}_\alpha^h, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha^h}{\partial r} \right) (F_\alpha^K)^2 d\xi \\ &\quad + \widehat{\phi}^i|_{\xi=-1} \widehat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha^K \left(\mathbf{u}_\alpha^h, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha^h}{\partial r} \right) 4\pi (r_\alpha^K)^2 - \widehat{\phi}^i|_{\xi=1} \widehat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha^{K+1} \left(\mathbf{u}_\alpha^h, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha^h}{\partial r} \right) 4\pi (r_\alpha^{K+1})^2. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

554 For a fixed element E_α^K , the corresponding set of equations in (B.2) can be written in matrix form as

$$\frac{d}{dt} (\mathbb{M}_\alpha^K \mathbf{U}_\alpha^K) = \mathbf{F}_\alpha^K, \quad \mathbb{M}_\alpha^K := \begin{bmatrix} M_\alpha^{K,0,0} \mathbb{I}_\alpha & \dots & M_\alpha^{K,0,p} \mathbb{I}_\alpha \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ M_\alpha^{K,p,0} \mathbb{I}_\alpha & \dots & M_\alpha^{K,p,p} \mathbb{I}_\alpha \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{U}_\alpha^K := \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_\alpha^{K,0} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{U}_\alpha^{K,p} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{F}_\alpha^K := \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{F}_\alpha^{K,0} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{F}_\alpha^{K,p} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{B.4})$$

570 the right, E_α^{K-1} , E_α^K . Following a similar approach than for $\mathbf{f}_\alpha^{\text{ALE}}$, the (approximate) derivatives of $\widehat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha^K$ and
 571 $\widehat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha^{K+1}$ required in (B.6)-(B.8) can be computed from the expressions

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \widehat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha^K}{\partial \mathbf{U}_\alpha^{K,j}} &= \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}_\alpha^{\text{diff}}}{\partial (\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha / \partial r)} \bigg|_{\left(\mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h,K+}, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h,K+}}{\partial r} \right)} \frac{1}{J_\alpha^K} \frac{d\widehat{\phi}^j}{d\xi} \bigg|_{\xi=-1} - \sigma_\alpha^K \frac{1}{J_\alpha^K} \frac{d\widehat{\phi}^j}{d\xi} \bigg|_{\xi=-1} \mathbb{I}_\alpha, \\ \frac{\partial \widehat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha^K}{\partial \mathbf{U}_\alpha^{K-1,j}} &= (v_\alpha - w_\alpha)_{r=r_\alpha^K} \widehat{\phi}^j \big|_{\xi=1} \mathbb{I}_\alpha + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}_\alpha^{\text{diff}}}{\partial (\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha / \partial r)} \bigg|_{\left(\mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h,K-}, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha^{h,K-}}{\partial r} \right)} \frac{1}{J_\alpha^{K-1}} \frac{d\widehat{\phi}^j}{d\xi} \bigg|_{\xi=1} + \sigma_\alpha^K \frac{1}{J_\alpha^{K-1}} \frac{d\widehat{\phi}^j}{d\xi} \bigg|_{\xi=1} \mathbb{I}_\alpha, \end{aligned}$$

572 with $\partial \mathbf{f}_\alpha^{\text{diff}} / \partial (\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha / \partial r) = \partial \mathbf{f}_\alpha^{\text{ALE}} / \partial (\partial \mathbf{u}_\alpha / \partial r)$, which is given by (B.9).

573 The integrals in the equations above are numerically computed using Gauss–Legendre quadrature rules
 574 [53] of $2p + 1$ nodes.

575 Appendix C. Initial condition

576 The initial condition assumes a droplet placed in an infinitely large, homogeneous gaseous environment.
 577 The gas-phase profiles of temperature and composition are estimated based on the analytically-integrated
 578 equations from [28], where the conservation of mass, energy and species (cf. Eq. (1)) are modified assuming
 579 a quasi-steady gas phase. This provides

$$\begin{aligned} Y_{g,f}(r, 0) &= 1 - (1 - Y_{g,f}|_{r=\infty}) \exp\left(\frac{-\dot{m}}{4\pi\rho_g D_{M,g} r}\right), \\ T_g(r, 0) &= T|_{r=a} - \frac{L_v + \dot{q}_s / \dot{m}}{c_p} + \left(T^\infty - T|_{r=a} + \frac{L_v + \dot{q}_s / \dot{m}}{c_p}\right) \exp\left(\frac{-\dot{m} c_p}{4\pi k_g r}\right), \end{aligned}$$

580 where L_v is the latent heat of evaporation, \dot{m} is the evaporated mass flow rate and \dot{q}_s is the sensible heat
 581 transfer rate. Assuming a known value for the droplet surface temperature $T|_{r=a}$, it is immediate to calculate
 582 the fuel mass fraction in the gas phase $Y_{g,f}|_{r=a}$ through liquid-vapor equilibrium (see Eq. (11)), and then \dot{m}
 583 and \dot{q}_s can be readily computed from the equations above by imposing

$$Y_{g,f}(a, 0) = Y_{g,f}|_{r=a}, \quad T_g(a, 0) = T|_{r=a}.$$

584 As for the temperature in the liquid phase, it is worth to note that a completely uniform temperature
 585 would not comply with the coupling conditions at the interface. Thus, the initial liquid temperature profile
 586 $T_l(r, 0)$ is adjusted using an exponential function so that most of the droplet remains at a uniform given
 587 temperature $T_{l,0}$, with a thin thermal boundary layer close to the interface that is adjusted through four
 588 fitting parameters (A, B, C, D) to fulfill these coupling conditions, as well as the symmetry conditions at
 589 $r = 0$. More specifically,

$$T_l(r, 0) = A + B r + C \exp\left(-\frac{a-r}{D}\right)$$

590 and

$$\frac{\partial T_l(r, 0)}{\partial r} \bigg|_{r=a} = \frac{\dot{q}_s}{k_l}, \quad T_l(r, 0)|_{r=a} = T|_{r=a}, \quad \frac{\partial T_l(r, 0)}{\partial r} \bigg|_{r=0} = 0, \quad T_l(r, 0)|_{r=0} = T_{l,0}.$$

591 See example in Fig. C.1. Since the droplet is assumed to be monocomponent, the composition profile in the
 592 liquid phase remains as $Y_{l,f}(r, 0) = 1$.

Figure C.1: Initial temperature profiles of the liquid and gas phases for an ethanol droplet at 300 K immersed in air at $T^\infty = 1000$ K.

593 Appendix D. Thermophysical properties used in the simulations

594 The numerical values of the thermophysical properties employed in the simulations presented in Section
595 5 are summarized in Table D.1.

Table D.1: Thermophysical properties used in each simulation.

Section	T^∞ [K]	ρ_l [kg/m ³]	ρ_g [kg/m ³]	$D_{T,l}$ [m ² /s]	$D_{T,g}$ [m ² /s]	$D_{M,g}$ [m ² /s]
5.1	1400	738.9	0.670	5.878E-08	2.705E-05	4.013E-05
5.2	400	782.3	1.061	8.635E-08	1.574E-05	1.463E-05
5.2	600	767.6	0.905	8.089E-08	1.885E-05	2.146E-05
5.2	800	761.1	0.796	7.855E-08	2.210E-05	2.863E-05
5.2	1000	757.1	0.712	7.716E-08	2.578E-05	3.636E-05
5.3	600	648.9	1.160	7.318E-08	1.204E-05	1.309E-05
5.3	800	642.7	1.053	7.162E-08	1.359E-05	1.739E-05
5.3	1000	639.4	0.954	7.084E-08	1.551E-05	2.200E-05
5.4, 5.5	1400	752.6	0.602	7.530E-08	3.367E-05	5.030E-05

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